

Technology in Hospitality

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Abstract:- Hospitality industry is one of the leading and driving forces industry in the global economy this industry has reshaped the way of service provided and received Due to the wide spread of the new technology. this research paper addresses how the new technology has developed in the hospitality industry and satisfied the guests needs and experiences and challenging the hotel industry service platform. As the technology is developed day-by-day we also focus on potential future hospitality service and further we discuss the fundamental challenges that to be overcome by the hospitality industry. The paper summaries the issues of technology in the hospitality industry in India. Key areas of issues are licenses, policies, cost and revenue management safety and security concerns and talent management etc.

The new trends that are grownup and dominating the market trends are to be discussed. The paper also concludes the suggestions to overcome with the key issues with benefits the industry to make better decisions.

Keywords:- Information Technology, Contactless Payments, Hospitality Trends, E-Commerce, Internet.

I. INTRODUCTION

By the word technology in hospitality describe a wide range of IT,E-Commerce, and similar technology with in the hospitality industry by the use of all this technology it makes the work life easy for the employees and improves the overall experience for hospitality customers.

All the new technology features can be achieved in the different way for example. Hospitality tech helps to improve the speed and work stress to the staff and also makes the work process fast and save money as well as time. Hospitality industry is a competitive industry it always should keep up with new technology which helps us in cost reduce, increase revenue generation potential and increase the customer expectation.

➤ Objective

On the basis of review of literatures this paper explains the important and development of the technology in the hospitality industry

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The main goal of this research paper is to identify the importance of technology in the hospitality industry. This research study is mainly based upon the collection of secondary data. Data was collected from various journals, Published research papers, Internet. Etc.

1.Robots in hotels & Restaurants:

Robots in the hospitality industry is the latest technology which is used in the hotels in the present days. This robot is replacing the human employment in this industry . These robots carry out the traditionally preformed tasks like welcoming guest, Providing Information to the customers

Few big brands of 5star hotels already has started the use of this robot for cleaning purpose , for killing germs etc.

2.Contactless Payment:

This contactless payment has become the most successful technology which is giving more comfort to the guest. At this present situation of COVID-19 most of the guest is preferring the Contactless payments. This contactless payment has many advantages for hotels, restaurants, bars and cafes this is why this technology has become the most important in the recent time

This contactless payment can be used even if the customers is not having their wallets with then in such cases they can use this facility. All the customers are satisfied with this type of facility that the hotel industry is providing to their guest.

3. Recognition Technology

This technology is the growing technology within the hospitality industry this has brought a high change. In particular, biometrics is being used to unlock the guest rooms and it is helpful to the hotel security to reduce their duty

By the use of this technology their will be less chances of robbery in the hotel rather than the guest no other person can open their room key. This technology needs the finger/face print to unlock the guest without the proper print it wont accesses to open the room door.

4. Chatbots:

Most of the service industry like pub, bar, restaurant, Hotels, etc. receives the queries from guest in different time. So answering to their queries at the different time is not possible to the employees because they may not available at all the time

This chat bots technology has many updated features like it will give the answer to all the basics questions that are asked by the customers without the help of the human involvements.

5. Mobile Check-In

This Mobile check-in technology has brought a great change in the hospitality industry. with this technology check-in can be done by the mobile. There will not be any interaction with the employee of the hotel and at this COVID situation most of the guest are using this technology to avoid meeting. This technology is beneficial because first impression is the last impression and give the customer ultimately feel about their visit or stay.

III. CONCLUSION

This research studies has given the idea that the hospitality industry is depended on the new technology that are updating in the market. As it is a service industry it should focus on the guest satisfaction by keeping the updated knowledge to the employees and technology to be used in the industry and marked as well. Also hotel should provide proper training to their employees regarding new technology that is using in the industry.

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